

A path to leadership in innovation for a developing country in Asia

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If a late-developing country follows an innovation path, we must proceed from the fact that the enterprises of this country lack innovative capacity. Therefore, it needs to succeed in technological catch up with developed countries (Miao et. al 2018). Generally speaking, the country's path to leadership of innovation can be divided into two stages: the investment or catching up one and the stage driven by ingenious innovation. The content of the policy areas and actors' activity comply with the country's stages of development including the resource stage, investment stage, and the stage grounded in the country's innovations (Porter, 1990). The development of the national innovation system should provide the fundamental basis for a country to pass these stages and win a leadership on each of these stages (Golichenko, 2016). The stage-based approach to determining policy dimensions and measures for carrying out these policies allows the state to promote the process of the co-evolution of absorption capacities (Castellacci and Natera, 2013). The results of the process enable increasing the innovative capacity of enterprises and the national innovation system as a whole (Hu and Mathews, 2005).

According to the methodology of the study, the national innovation system is represented as three interconnected macroblocks. These are the business environment and the market; the environment generating new knowledge; and mechanisms for transferring knowledge (Golichenko 2013). In this study, the block of mechanisms of knowledge transfer is decomposed into three interacting channels of knowledge transfer: open information channels; those of a transformation of open knowledge into pre-competitive and competitive one; and channels of commercial knowledge transfer. The use of the channels depends heavily on the models of innovative activity firms. In the paper, two basic models of actors' behaviour are considered. The first one corresponds to the investment stage of the country's development. The main driver of the stage is the technology catch-up. The second type is associated with the development driven by ingenious or radical innovations.

For the late developing country using global market technology in catch-up processes, the active usage of open knowledge transfer channels and commercial knowledge transfer channels is of the utmost importance. Moreover, as the practice shows (OECD, 2014, 2016), to achieve large-scale processes for creating innovative products, the domestic enterprises must actively invest in R&D. Since the driver of the country's development is external demand, it is impossible to organize the catching-up of technologies without establishing the interaction of domestic enterprises with modern global value chains (GVC). In the paper, the block of business and market environment is decomposed according to the hierarchy of GVC (Amador and Cabrial, 2016). The enterprises of the catching-up country are the easiest to integrate into the GVCs that have a modular production system. The GVC of some types of R&D-intensive products give useful examples of such chains whose openness and fragmentation provide favourable opportunities for a catching-up country.

The step to the next level of innovation leadership is to do a transition to the driven by ingenious innovation. However, there is a danger that the country having coped successfully with the passage of many phases during the investment stage will become "stuck" on it and not be able to move to the next stage. It is therefore essential to create the necessary institution's conditions and resources supporting the transition to the stage.

At the stage, the demand-pull policy should influence innovation by reducing barriers to innovation activity and stimulating demand-pull (Edler, 2007). It ought to facilitate both the origin of new markets and the reconstruction of established markets (OECD, 2011b). It should be noted that the public policy of technology push has to encourage the firms whose activities are related to high technologies to shaping and extending research knowledge bases (Edler, J.

and J., Fagerberg, 2017). It forces the firm to form a particular knowledge base that is hard to imitate or replicate by its competitors (Grimpe and Kaiser, 2010). The uniqueness of this research knowledge base is enhanced by the usage of tacit knowledge of the firm's highly skilled personnel. Strengthening the knowledge base is facilitated by the organisational capability and routines of the firm, which allow efficiently managing this base.

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